

Review Article

Exploring the Longevity Secrets of Ikaria: A Review of Anecdotal Evidence and Scientific Insights

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Received: 17 May 2025

Accepted: 21 May 2025

Published: 29 May 2025

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Abstract

Ikaria, a Greek island situated in the eastern Aegean Sea, is one of the five Blue Zones globally, known for its exceptional longevity and high life expectancy. This paper explores both anecdotal evidence and research findings to uncover the secrets of healthy aging in Ikaria. Through firsthand observations and conversations with locals, this short communication highlights key habits that contribute to longevity, including physical activity, diet, socializing, and lifestyle factors such as decreased stress, slow-paced living and afternoon naps. The integration of environmental, behavioral, cultural and clinical factors is examined to understand how these elements collectively shape the health and longevity of Ikarians.

Introduction

Ikaria is a Greek island that is part of the renowned Blue Zones, which include Nicosia (Costa Rica), San Francisco (USA), Okinawa (Japan), and Sardinia (Italy). The island is often referred to as the place where people “forget to die,” due to its remarkable population of centenarians. My two visits to the island provided an opportunity to immerse myself in the local culture, engage in conversations with residents, and explore the longevity practices that contribute to the health of its people. In this brief review, I will offer anecdotal insights drawn from conversations with Ikarians, share my behavioral observations, and summarize current research on the factors that contribute to healthy aging on the island.

Anecdotal Insights from Locals

During my visit on arrival, I was invited to a wedding by a taxi driver, who suggested that I, along with other tourists sharing the ride, should attend the celebration. This warmth and hospitality are reflective of the relaxed and slow-paced lifestyle that characterizes the Ikarians. There were close to five hundred guests at the wedding, which included guests who had never met the bride and groom. It was during this wedding that I heard a story from one of the locals about an Ikarian man who woke up one morning to water his vegetables but, upon encountering a neighbor who invited him for coffee, spent a few hours chatting. Later, as he continued on his journey to go to the farm he was invited by another neighbor for lunch, and by the time he finished, he decided to postpone his farmwork until the next day. This story highlights the laid-back attitude of the locals, who prioritize social connections and avoid rushing through life. The lack of stress and the ability to enjoy life at a leisurely pace is a fundamental part of their longevity.

Health Practices and Habits of Ikarians

One of the most striking features of the Ikaria population is their healthy aging habits. According to the Ikaria Study, a large proportion of the island’s elderly population, particularly those over 80, reported daily physical activity, healthy eating habits, avoidance of smoking, frequent social interactions, midday naps, and remarkably low rates of depression [1].

These factors appear to be key contributors to the longevity observed on the island. In the past, local inhabitants would walk a lot on this mountainous is-land to get from one town to the next. The religious and cultural festivities in Ikaria bring young and old people together, up to four generations jointly celebrate and enjoy good local food, wine, traditional music and dances until the early hours of the morning.

Scientific Insights into Longevity

Legrand et al. found that social factors play a key role in Ikaria’s longevity, with strong family solidarity and low institutionalization [2]. Ikarian residents have maintained their traditions and manual occupations, with much of their food being locally produced [2-5].

The majority of the Oldest Old maintained daily social interactions and participated in social events (e.g., religious festivals), and some inhabitants continued working, supporting social integration. Adherence to the Mediterranean diet was good, aided by local food production, and physical activity levels were high, particularly among men, due to continued agricultural work. A study assessing the impact of these factors on longevity in Ikaria would be valuable [2,4].

The health benefits of physical activity, a core aspect of Ikarian life, have been well documented. Regular physical exercise has been associated with lower rates of cardiovascular disease, obesity, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus [6]. Additionally, physical activity has been shown to protect against arrhythmias and improve cardiovascular health. For elderly individuals, even those who are obese, physical activity has beneficial effects on heart health, including a reduction in left ventricular hypertrophy and improved autonomic function. This aligns with findings that increased physical activity promotes long-term health and well-being.

The diet also plays a critical role in the health of Ikarians. The Mediterranean diet, which is rich in plant-based foods, healthy fats, and moderate consumption of fish, is central to the Ikarian lifestyle. Adherence to this diet has been linked to improved aortic elasticity and reduced prevalence

of hyperuricemia, which is often elevated in elderly populations [2]. The combination of healthy dietary practices and daily physical activity forms a protective barrier against many age-related diseases.

The importance of social connections cannot be overstated. Ikarians maintain close-knit communities, with frequent socializing being a common part of their daily routine. This social interaction is thought to reduce feelings of isolation, improve mental health, and contribute to emotional well-being, which is crucial for successful aging. Ikarians eagerly anticipate numerous religious festivals held across different parts of the island, where people of all ages come together to celebrate with traditional dancing, local cuisine, and live music. What stood out to me was seeing young children—some under the age of ten—staying up well into the early morning hours, playing with peers of all ages and actively participating in the traditional dances.

Conclusion

The longevity of the Ikarian population can be attributed to a combination of modifiable lifestyle factors, including physical activity, a healthy diet, social engagement, afternoon naps, and minimal stress due to the relaxed way of living. These findings suggest that a balanced approach, integrating environmental, behavioral, cultural and clinical characteristics as well as lifestyle factors may hold the key to longevity. As we explore the “secrets” of Ikaria, it becomes clear that the interaction between individual habits and the broader cultural context contributes to the island’s exceptional health outcomes. Ultimately, the Ikarian example offers valuable insights

Cite this article: Peter Kyriakoulis. (2025) Exploring the Longevity Secrets of Ikaria: A Review of Anecdotal Evidence and Scientific Insights. *Advance Medical & Clinical Research* 6 (1): 106-107.

into the factors that contribute to successful aging and highlights the importance of adopting a holistic approach to health and wellness.

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